

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

A study on impact of conceptual and practical based learning on employability

Zaker Ul Oman *, Sumeet Pandey and Ashitosh Gaddam

Department of Commerce, Avinash College of Commerce, Himayathnagar, Hyderabad, Telangana State, 500029, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(02), 486–492

Publication history: Received on 02 October 2022; revised on 08 November 2022; accepted on 11 November 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.2.1204>

Abstract

The impact of practical learning on employability is significant. There is no age, time or effort limit to learn because it is what as a person important to survive and thrive in this world. Although learning through theory is one side of the mirror, leveraging the knowledge in real world is what matters most. As employability is the primary goal, the process of learning leading up to that is what supports the goal. To assist the above statements this study refers the teaching strategies and learning models states that learning and employability are correlated for both learners and their peers. Practical-based learning should be implemented in the current scenario. It must be started from the preparatory level to make it a habit. The main aim of education is "learning" which must not miss out from the education system as learning has a direct impact on employability.

The study reveals that a variety of techniques can be implemented by peers and the participation of students in the process could be a productive way to collaborate, hence, this kind of engagement would be a superior course of action for students to learn practically and can increase the scope of employability. The relevant articles' conclusions were discussed for better understanding of perceptions, multiple learning models and their importance, and significance are acknowledged to comprehend the impact of conceptual learning on Employability. The methods such as Practical Based Learning provide students' exposure to real-life problems that they can solve by adopting the learning methods.

Keywords: Teaching Strategies; Learning Models; Conceptual Teaching; Practical based learning impact on employability

1 Introduction

The "Learning and employability framework" is an effort to get beyond the shortcomings of well-known employability models, which are either too complicated or lack operational clarity. The model links learning process, learning environment, and learning outcomes to employability and identifies novel elements of employability not taken into account in other studies.

Numerous studies have been conducted on employability and the contributing factors. The learning experiences of university students have previously been studied with a focus on career development initiatives, internships, work experience initiatives, soft skill development initiatives, and even university admission requirements. The emphasis on these outside variables and how they affect employability seems to have diverted focus from "learning," the primary goal of higher education. Numerous studies have focused on the learning that occurs in universities, but because various learning models and methodologies are taken into account, it is challenging to reach a consensus.

Although learning and employability are unmistakably complementary concepts, there is a lack of clarity and representation in this relationship. The current study resolves this problem by offering a paradigm that convincingly

* Corresponding author: Zaker Ul Oman

Department of Commerce, Avinash College of Commerce, Himayathnagar, Hyderabad, Telangana State, 500029, India.

contrasts learning and employability in a way that is both simple to comprehend and offers essential theoretical backing. Two novel factors—university reputation and learning outcomes and their impact on graduate employment—were identified by a thorough study of the literature on employability and learning. University reputation appears to regulate the association between learning outcomes and employability, whereas learning outcomes appear to mediate the relationship between lower-tier employability skills and employability. The "learning and employability framework" can be seen as a timely and pertinent study since it is clear enough for students, parents, employers, and professors to understand while also giving the research community the necessary operational clarity and theoretical support. For those wishing to create curricula and pedagogical approaches that will maximize employability, the framework offers guidance.

Objectives

- To understand the effectiveness of Practical and Conceptual based Learning.
- To evaluate the impact of Conceptual & Practical based Learning on Employability.

2 Research methodology

The proposed study mainly is descriptive in nature. It solely relies on secondary data and information that is gathered from pertinent books, reviewed well answered literature, documents from different organizations, education based articles, papers, and websites to increase the effectiveness of the study.

3 Literature review

Although learning and employability seem to be closely related and complementary study notions (Knight & Yorke, 2003), there isn't much research on these two ideas and how they relate, which makes it difficult to grasp how they relate. A review of the literature demonstrates unequivocally that employability is a heavily researched topic, with particular attention paid to developing more effective pedagogical tools like business simulations (Avramenko, 2011), suggesting curriculum improvements to suit various social practices and identities (Holmes, 2001), student perspectives on employability (Tymon, 2013), lecturer perceptions of employability (Morrison, 2013), graduates' career orientation and attitude toward work (Tomlinson, 2013), and more (Alexandrea, 2009). One of the primary purposes of a university education—learning—seems to have been neglected in favor of the concentration on these many subject areas and their impact on employability. A clear understanding of the critical relationship between learning and employability is essential because employability is regarded as the benefit and usefulness of study programs for career and work tasks (Storen & Aamodt, 2010) and because there is credible evidence to support the assertion that individual learners, learning environments, workplaces, and study repositories are said to form a "ecology" leading to employability learning (O'Donoghue & Maguire, 2005). www.ccsenet.org/jel Vol. 4, No. 2 of the Journal of Education and Learning, 2015 The underlying elements determining university graduates' employability have been the subject of numerous research, although the outcomes have varied. (Smith et al., 2014; Finch et al., 2013; Wickramasighe & Perera, 2010; Pool & Sewell, 2007) which unequivocally shows the neglect of employability studies. This disagreement can be directly linked to the politicization of the notion by the government, business, and higher education sectors (Smith et al., 2014), where various parties with different stakes in the concept define it in ways that fit their objectives. Several theoretical models of employability can be found among the numerous studies on employability and its underlying elements (Pool & Sewell, 2007).

One of the most often used employability models, the "Career EDGE framework of employability," seems to compile more than five decades' worth of research on employability from many scholars. (Robbins, 1963; Hillage & Pollard, 1998; de la Harpe et al., 2000; Knight & Yorke, 2004; Wickramasighe & Perera, 2010; Finch et al., 2013; Smith et al., 2014). The complexity and lack of research support found in earlier employability models, such as "USEM" (Knight & Yorke, 2002), "employability skills" (Cotton, 1993), and "course providers model" (Bennette, 1999), appear to be resolved by the career EDGE model, which is now regarded as a widely accepted employability model (Phillips et al., 2010). The "Learning and Employability Framework" was created based on the five (05) lower-level employment skill constructs listed in the Career EDGE framework: Emotional Intelligence, General Skills, Degree Subject Knowledge, Skills and Understanding, and Work and Life Experience. Based on several learning models and definitions, studies on learning appear to span a wide range of topics, with the widely used LEPO model (Learning Environment, Process, and Outcome) proposed by Phillips et al. (2010) It seems to deliver much-needed simplicity that is necessary for current research. This study finds a correlation between Career EDGE's lower-level employability skill components and the LEPO model's learning process and learning environment. Therefore, it is possible to contend that learning outcomes act as a mediator between employability and learning (process and environment). The fact that "learning outcomes"

play a mediating function in the "learning and employability framework" is corroborated by a number of additional studies (Finch et al., 2013; Knight & Yorke, 2002). In addition, institution and program reputation are thought to affect graduate employability (Finch et al., 2013). Since graduates are more likely to find employment at "better" universities, employability levels are greater. (Ciriaci & Muscio, 2010) It suggests that the association between learning results and employability is moderated by a university's reputation.

Considering Education and Employability A significant flaw in current employability research appears to be the scant attention paid to conceptualizing learning and employability as different study concepts (Smith et al., 2014). Awareness the ontological and epistemological presumptions in the study field will be aided by having a comprehensive understanding of the existing research, especially the primary theoretical frameworks on employability, learning, and their relationships. First, a historical perspective is used to describe the idea of employability, and a precise definition that applies to the current study is provided. 2.1 Employability and Current Frameworks for Employability. The idea of employment is not new, and early studies like the "Robbins report," which named employability as one of the four fundamental goals of higher education, can be considered as focusing on employability (Robbins, 1963). Employability has been defined clearly using the results of previous studies, however these attempts (Hillage & Pollard, 1998) seem to lack generalizability because they are mostly focused on case study approaches (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2010). Given that the term "employability" is ill-defined (Hillage & Pollard, 1998), a number of prevalent meanings were taken into consideration (Smith et al., 2014; Pool & Sewell, 2007; Knight & Yorke, 2002). The Confederation of British Industry's (CBI's) definition of employability, which reads in part as follows: "Employability is a set of attributes, skills, and knowledge that all labor market participants should possess to ensure they have the capability of being effective in the workplace—to the benefit of themselves, their employer, and the wider economy" (Confederation of British Industry, 2009), seems to cover the impact of employability on www.ccsenet.org/jel, Journal of The widespread politicization of the idea has led to a lack of consensus over the precise definition of employability, which has stymied advancements in this field (Smith, Ferns, & Russell, 2014). As intricate and varied as employability definitions are the theoretical models used to describe the fundamental components of employability and how they interact. In order for non-experts like teachers, students, and parents to understand the employability skills models, such as USEM (Understanding, Skills, Efficacy Beliefs, and Meta-cognition), Knight and Yorke presented them in 2002 as part of the ESECT (Enhancing Student Employability Co-ordination Team) project. The Career EDGE framework made an effort to make the notion simple and clear for easy understanding (Pool & Sewell, 2007), but the lack of adequate research backing seems to have diminished its utility. The Career EDGE framework seems to be a thorough representation of employability, although the usage of a snapshot method lessens its value (Smith et al., 2014). Despite the extensive research backing, some exploratory studies on employability like Finch et al. (2013) and conceptual models on employability like Smith et al. (2014) seem to be too complex to allow for simple understanding. The employability paradigm used in the current study is an effort to balance simplicity and clarity without sacrificing the research foundation.

4 Teaching strategies for problem based learning

In problem-based learning (PBL), students attempt to solve an issue or a series of problems that are novel to them. Because PBL is based on a constructivist philosophy, it encourages active learning. Students participate in activities in groups, usually during tutorials or seminars.

Some of the strategies to be followed to make a session effective and give proper learning outcome

- Planning a Session.
- Questioning Strategies.
- Class Room Assessment Test (CAT's).
- Situational-Based Learning.
- Case Method.
- Impact of practical based learning

"Teachers who are most familiar with that place because they work there every day are the ones who best understand what that school needs or might be able to create!" Timothy Moss.

You must have a deeper understanding of who you are as a professional (and as a person).

Practice-based teaching courses are current and responsive, and you get support as you get started in a classroom.

4.1 Outcomes of Practical based learning

- Retains Information for longer period.
- Active Learning
- Engaging
- Developing Fine Motor Skills
- Eliminates the Process of Mugging
- Encourages Self Learning
- More Interactive Sessions
- Industry Ready
- Practice Makes Man Perfect
- Inter Relation with Theory
- Career Planner
- Helps You Envision Real Life Situations

5 Learning models to improve your learning ability

Your learning preferences can be determined rather easily. You can either focus on your favourite teaching technique or take an online test. Knowing the different learning styles will make this decision much easier for you.

As a result, if you consider yourself a visual learner, you may devote more effort to understanding how the VARK model works. To improve your learning abilities, look into specific learning strategies for this learning style.

It is clear that learning is a difficult process in the end. If you can successfully break this complex phenomenon, you can employ it extremely effectively. Learning will no longer be an issue for you now that you are equipped with all the knowledge you need about learning models, and you are prepared for life.

5.1 Kolb Learning Style Model

The experiential learning hypothesis is another name for this type of learning.

5.2 VARK Learning Style Model

The learning model itself is explained by the abbreviation VARK. It stands for kinesthetic, reading/writing, auditory, visual, and visual-auditory learning methods. According to this paradigm, each learner goes through one of three steps when learning.

5.3 Gregorc Learning Model

The Gregorc learning model probes the inner workings of the mind.

5.4 Hermann Brain Dominance

A tool to determine people's preferred methods of learning was developed with the Hermann Brain Dominance Instrument (HBDI).

5.5 4MAT Learning Model

The Kolb model is expanded upon by the 4MAT learning model. But it offers four distinct learning approaches, including creative, analytical, dynamic, and common sense.

5.6 Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model

This learning approach is concentrated on the idea that each person has a unique preference for how they prefer to absorb new information. Some people might have numerous preferences, some might switch between them, and some might only have one.

5.7 Honey Mumford Model

The Kolb model and the Honey Mumford model are quite similar. The following learning modes are introduced:

- Activists: Students who are active learners use what they learn in real-world situations.
- Theorists: These are individuals who enjoy learning from already-established facts and statistics.
- Pragmatists: These people conceptualize and test concepts before learning from them.
- Reflectors: These students consider what they observe and what they can learn from it.

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, cases are a useful technique for learning to take place. It requires some preparation on both the teacher's and the students' parts, but don't overlook these advantages (Bruner, 2002):

- Both the teacher and the pupils should be learning. The teacher frequently "encounters fresh perspective on old difficulties or tests classic solutions to new problems" because of the participatory nature of this approach.
- The pupils are enthusiastic, engaged, and having fun. If done correctly, the pupils are collaborating with one another to support one another. Try not to dominate the conversation or act as the "sage on the stage." If you are, pupils are not actively engaged with the content as the case method enables, but rather are just absorbing it.
- Wait until the students have completed sharing their points of view before adding your own. Before adding to or changing the conversation, wait and observe their body language.
- Keep track of the discussion's development and topics. One method is to structure the remarks using the board or computer. The two-column method is an additional approach that is particularly helpful when there is a conflict or numerous possibilities. Before any debates or evaluations take place, each argument or opinion is listed in the appropriate column. Don't forget to provide any supporting data. You can use debates, role-plays, and simulations in addition to the discussion approach to draw out the case's lesson.
- Make sure your grading system accurately and logically represents the contributions if you chose to grade participation.

Suggestions

- Overall Learning
 - The context must be properly explained to demonstrate why it is essential to completing the assignment and how it relates to the students' point of view.
 - The task's objective must coincide with the level of structure placed on the issue or query.
 - It's crucial to accurately estimate the time needed, taking into account time for contemplation and first-response improvement.
 - Clearly defining and carefully negotiating the roles of external participants, organizations, and employers.
- For Students
 - Exercise self-management and time management skills;
 - Participate in task decision-making;
 - Be able to communicate and share their ideas;
 - Exercise a systematic approach to problem-solving;
 - Know how to seek information from different sources;
 - Collaborate with others; and Be Given Opportunities to Take Pride in Their Work;
- For Teachers
 - Strike a balance between didactic instruction and autonomous inquiry to guarantee that students reach a specific level of knowledge and proficiency before being at ease working alone or in groups;
 - Initiate and oversee unstructured class discussion;
 - Place new knowledge in the perspective of earlier knowledge;
 - Ensuring that pupils experience and advance through each stage of the inquiry or problem-solving process;
 - Put students in groups as necessary for the activity;
 - Base student guidance on the teacher's knowledge of the students' developing conceptual understanding, for instance in science;

- Outline the connections between the practical activity and the conceptual theory, especially those across disciplines; and give students time to reflect after the practice.
- Assessment
 - Student development needs to be regularly assessed and documented, both by the students themselves and by their peers.
 - Evaluation tools should monitor development of content (knowledge acquisition) and mental habits (character and dispositions for learning).

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We would like to acknowledge all the Lecturers of Avinash College of Commerce (HTN) for their prompt participation and enlighten the study with their years of experience in teaching and learning process.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest with the study that the authors of this paper need to report.

References

- [1] Yorke, M., Knight, P. (2003). *Assessment Learning and Employability*. United Kingdom: McGraw-Hill Education.
- [2] Avramenko, R. (2011). *Courage: The Politics of Life and Limb*. United States: University of Notre Dame Press.
- [3] Holmes, J. (2001). *An Introduction to Sociolinguistics*. Spain: Longman.
- [4] Alex Tymon (2013) The student perspective on employability, *Studies in Higher Education*, 38:6, 841-856, DOI: 10.1080/03075079.2011.604408
- [5] Rennie, F., & Morrison, T. (2012). *e-Learning and Social Networking Handbook: Resources for Higher Education* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203120279>
- [6] *Developing Materials for Language Teaching*. (2013). United Kingdom: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- [7] Alexandra, F., Portelaa, M., & Sáa, C. (2009). Admission conditions and graduates' employability. *Studies in Higher Education*, 34(7), 795-805. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03075070802688553>
- [8] Støren, L. A., & Aamodt, P. O. (2010). The quality of higher education and employability of graduates. *Quality in Higher Education*, 16(3), 297-313.
- [9] O'Donoghue, J., & Maguire, T. (2005). The individual learner, employability and the workplace: a reappraisal of relationships and prophecies. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 29(6), 436-446.
- [10] Smith, K., Woodward, A., Campbell-Lendrum, D., Chadee, D., Honda, Y., Liu, Q. & BUTLER, C. (2014). Human health: impacts, adaptation, and co-benefits. In *Climate Change 2014: impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Part A: global and sectoral aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the fifth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (pp. 709-754). Cambridge University Press.
- [11] Finch, D. J., Hamilton, L. K., Baldwin, R., & Zehner, M. (2013). An exploratory study of factors affecting undergraduate employability. *Education+ Training*.
- [12] Wickramasinghe, V., & Perera, L. (2010). Graduates', university lecturers' and employers' perceptions towards employability skills. *Education+ Training*.
- [13] Pool, L. D., & Sewell, P. (2007). The key to employability: developing a practical model of graduate employability. *Education+ Training*.
- [14] De la Harpe, B., & Radloff, A. (2000). Informed teachers and learners: The importance of assessing the characteristics needed for lifelong learning. *Studies in Continuing education*, 22(2), 169-182.
- [15] Hillage, J., & Pollard, E. (1998). *Employability: developing a framework for policy analysis*.
- [16] Robbins, L. C. (1963). The accuracy of parental recall of aspects of child development and of child rearing practices. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 66(3), 261.

- [17] Knight-and-Yorke-(2002). Manufacturing excellent engineers: Skill development in a Master's programme - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/USEM-model-of-employability-_fig1_288656908 [accessed 7 Nov, 2022]
- [18] Cotton, J. L. (1993). Employee involvement: Methods for improving performance and work attitudes. Sage Publications, Inc.
- [19] Bennett RJ, et al. (1999) Binding specificity determines polarity of DNA unwinding by the Sgs1 protein of *S. cerevisiae*. *J Mol Biol* 289(2):235-48
- [20] Phillips, John & Muheim, Rachel & Jorge, Paulo. (2013). Phillips et al. 2010 (RSIF).
- [21] Ciriaci, D., & Muscio, A. (2010). Does university choice drive graduates' employability?
- [22] Hillage, J. and Pollard, E. (1998) Employability: Developing a Framework for Policy Analysis. Department for Education and Employment, London. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/225083565_Employability_Developing_a_framework_for_policy_analysis_London_DfEE
- [23] Wickramasinghe, V. and Perera, L. (2010) Graduates', University Lecturers' and Employers' Perceptions towards Employability Skills. *Education & Training*, 52, 226-244. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00400911011037355>
- [24] Pool, L. D., & Sewell, P. (2007). The Key to Employability: Developing a Practical Model of Graduate Employability. *Education+Training*, 49, 277-289. <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/pdfplus/10.1108/00400910710754435> <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00400910710754435>
- [25] <https://www.zaubacorp.com/company/THE-CONFEDERATION-OF-BRITISH-INDUSTRY/F03879#:~:text=The%20Confederation%20of%20British%20Industry%20is%20a%20foreign,Industry%27s%20Foreign%20Company%20Registration%20Number%20%28FCRN%29%20is%20F03879>.
- [26] <https://www.lifehack.org/870267/learning-models>
- [27] <https://citl.illinois.edu/citl-101/teaching-learning/resources/teaching-strategies>
- [28] <https://www.torrens.edu.au/blog/practice-based-learning-for-educators>
- [29] <https://collegemarker.com/blogs/practical-learning-the-best-way-forward/>
- [30] <https://www.tes.com/magazine/teaching-learning/general/practical-learning-why-and-how-you-should-embed-it>